

**FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY: UNDERSTANDING LOCAL
CSO STRATEGIES FOR REDUCING DONOR DEPENDENCE IN
SOUTH WEST NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The civil society sector is evolving in scope and scale in a time when foreign aid is diminishing and there is a drastic cut in international government grants. Many studies conducted have focused on the role of civil society in development especially poverty eradication in Nigeria. However, very few researches have focused on the financial sustainability of local civil society organisations in Nigeria. This research bridged this gap in knowledge by uncovering insights on how donor-dependent CSOs have diversified their revenue streams, with a specific focus on commercial activities. The central research question is “What strategies are particularly contributing to the financial sustainability of local CSOs in Nigeria?”

This research used a qualitative method to collect data through open-ended survey questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, while assessing five local CSOs founded between the year 1999 and 2007 in Nigeria. The research result reveals that local CSOs are striving for sustainability through diversification of locally available and sustainable resources to reduce donor dependence and achieve some degree of autonomy.

It also contributes to the theoretical debates on the asymmetrical donor-CSO relationship by revealing three mechanisms of donor’s influence, including control of funding, funding priorities and programme accountability. These mechanisms have however resulted in discernible effects on the behaviour of CSOs such as mission or goal displacement effect, exclusion of vulnerable groups, and issue of legitimacy.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that no portion of the work referred to in this dissertation has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification of this or any other university or other institutes of learning.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
LCSO	Local Civil Society Organisation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Commission and Development
RDT	Resource Dependence Theory
USAID	United States Agency for International Development

CHAPTER ONE

1.1 INTRODUCTION

For over three decades, there has been a rise in the involvement of civil society organisations (CSOs) in development. The observable deficiencies in government-led development programmes between the 1970s and 1980s incited interests in CSOs as alternative development agent with the capacity for social mobilisation (Banks and Hulme, 2012; Bebbington, 2005). As a result, international organisations including bilateral, multilateral and multi-bi aid providers increasingly seek to allocate development assistance through local CSOs (LCSOs). CSOs are now the new sweetheart of development. A resolute principle of CSO legitimacy in the development process is premised on its effectiveness and efficiency in attaining development goals, meeting the needs of the poor and reducing inequality (Lewis, 2007; Ilhan et al. 2013).

However, the impact of worsening global economic conditions and subsequent recessions have reduced the resources available for CSOs in Nigeria (Adeyeye, 2016). The purpose of this dissertation is to shed light on this issue by investigating how LCSOs are achieving financial sustainability.

1.2 RESEARCH CONTEXT AND PROBLEM

In 2008, Nigeria emerged as a lower-middle-income country with the highest poor population living below \$1 per day, implying that there is a surge in poverty rate (Glenie, 2011; World Bank, 2007). CSOs are at the frontline of development, championing grassroots service delivery, responding to humanitarian emergencies, meeting economic, social and environmental demands (Lewis and Kanji, 2009).

As the international aid system is rapidly facing critical threat due to funding constraints, the majority of local CSOs in developing countries are also struggling to be financially viable. Within the international development system, there are over forty bilateral and multilateral donors including twenty-six United Nations agencies and over twenty global, and regional financial institutions such as world bank. Northern countries signed an agreement to provide 0.7 per cent of their annual GNP towards southern countries development (OECD, 2013). However, bi and

multi-lateral aid allocation to middle-income countries have been reduced by one-third (Glenie, 2011; Agg, 2006). Between 2014 and 2016, various studies show that CSOs in lower-middle-income countries including Nigeria are facing financial sustainability issues partly as a result of a change in the aid-allocation landscape (INTRAC, 2014; Arhin, et.al, 2018; Dubochet, 2012). As at 2018, over 92,000 national CSOs were estimated to be registered with the Corporate Affairs Commission of Nigeria (USAID, 2019), of which only about 74 local CSOs are currently active in the south-west, Nigeria (Yerima, 2017).

Southern CSOs have become accustomed to northern donors' grants even though most of the grants have limitations (Holloway, 2001), and once the grant is exhausted, they become vulnerable to closure (Hailey & Salway, 2016), forced to downsize and lay off employees. Lewis and Kanji (2009, pp.171) assert that activities of NGOs, the large subset of CSOs, are primarily funded by the "grant model" in which donors provide grant funding in form of cash or in-kind. And the "sub-contracting model", in which donors especially bilateral donors provide funds to CSOs to implement contracted projects. Consequently, CSOs have been criticised for over-reliance on donor funding (Fowler 2016), being too close to funders agenda and moving away from the grassroots or project beneficiary (Ibrahim and Hulme, 2011).

The funding environments for civil society are changing accordingly and CSOs are restructuring due to financial constraints (USAID, 2019). Ultimately, CSO leaders are becoming resilient and keen to adapt to the uncertainties and change by re-inventing and managing any downturn. It is for this reason that the researcher decided to explore the key strategies that local CSOs in Nigeria have used to weather financial storm while maximising their value of solving societal problems.

1.3 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH DESIGN

A qualitative study was conducted to explore and provide valuable insights into the financial sustainability of CSOs in Nigeria. This is a difficult issue to investigate, as traditional CSOs have a fixed funding model and a culture of donor-dependence, hence finance is a highly sensitive topic, with most CSOs reluctant to openly discuss it. To investigate this phenomenon, the researcher first identified five local CSOs and then selected a sample of participants which included six organisation leaders. Data collection was conducted through survey questionnaires and semi-

structured interviews between July and August 2020 to examine the CSOs financial sustainability strategies. The findings revealed that CSOs receive donor funding and non-financial resources from different sources both locally and internationally. The findings also indicated that CSOs are subjected to external power and influence.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The chapters in this dissertation raise fascinating and critical questions for understanding the funding strategies of CSOs and the impact of these strategies on the organisations.

Central Questions:

- What strategies are particularly contributing to the financial sustainability of local CSOs in Nigeria, allowing these organisations to reduce donor dependence and continue their development work?

Sub-questions

- What are the factors that influence the local CSOs' adoption of diversified revenue streams?
- How do donors support the financial sustainability of CSOs?
- What evidence is there of donor power being exerted on CSOs?
- What are the effects of these strategies on the CSO's mission and programs?

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This research could be used by leaders in the civil society sector to understand and adopt the best practices for financial management and sustainability. The study outcome could also be relevant to researchers and scholars as it will form the foundation for future researches and discussions relating to CSO and financial sustainability. In terms of the theoretical approach, the research is based on Resource dependency theory (RDT) for addressing organisations' resource challenges.

This dissertation is a compilation of six chapters. This chapter has presented the background of the study and then highlighted its objectives and questions. The next chapter (two) reviews

literature about CSO revenue diversification as well as it presents the theoretical framework – Resource dependency theory (RDT). Chapter three covers the overall methodology approaches including data collection and analysis processes. Chapter four and five details the study findings based on key themes that emerged during analysis. Chapter six discusses the relevance of this study to wider academia and the civil society sector, research limitations and conclusion.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL DISCUSSION

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter analyses substantial discussions and arguments surrounding civil society organisation's financial sustainability, resource mobilisation, revenue diversification and social enterprise from various research works and literature including academic peer-reviewed publications (articles & books), international development articles and government report. It comprises of nineteen works of literature published between 2010 and 2018 and thirteen published in 2009 or earlier, all identified and sourced through library search and the internet. The last section of this chapter is comprehensive literature on the theoretical framework – Resource Dependence Theory, which provides the baseline for this study.

2.2 A LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1.1 Financially Sustainable Organisation

To assess the strategies that contribute to CSOs financial sustainability, it is crucial to conceptualise what makes a financially sustainable organisation. According to Bowman (2011), financial sustainability is defined as the ability of an organisation to uphold long-term “financial capacity”. Financial capacity is the principal resources an organisation needs to grapple opportunities, improve programme activities and develop resilience to counter unforeseen risks in the short-term while trying to manage organisational operations. This definition declares the inextricable link between funding and mission and indicates the short- and long-term goals for organisational viability. An alternative definition proposed by Leon (2001, pp.14) was established on the principles of an accounting system and implied that CSOs cannot attain long-term financial sustainability without securing more revenues than its actual expenses. Bowman (2011) and Leon (2001) definitions highlight how strengthening financial capacity guarantees the continuance of the organisation's activities over time. Furthermore, Hailey and Salway (2016) and Mitchell (2012) describe sustainable CSOs as organisations having the capacity to withstand the change in external factors and mitigate risks through revenue diversification.

Overall, there appears to be a consensus about the description of a financially sustainable organisation among these authors, reflecting the dynamic and changeable nature of the organisations to become less vulnerable to external financial shocks and shortages in cash-flow. This next section will provide a comprehensive analysis of how sustainable CSOs are mobilising resources to build financial reserves.

2.1.2 Resource Diversification

Diversification means acquiring both unrestricted financial and non-financial resources from various sources. Alymkulova and Seipulnik (2005) agree with Berrett and Holliday (2018) that the most common financing strategy for CSOs is resource diversification which enables these organisations to balance their dependence on earned revenues and reserves. Fowler (2000, pp.62) claims that organisations can ‘limit their dependence on foreign aid by diversifying their revenue’ to improve CSOs’ financial health (Alymkulova & Seipulnik, 2005; Mitchell, 2012; Rasler, 2007) and reduce the impact of changes in various revenue streams (Aschari-Lincoln & Jager, 2016; Chikoto and Neely, 2014). These authors argued that CSOs that adopt resource diversification can control the acquisition of resources from the environment and thereby attain some level of financial autonomy.

According to Berrett and Holliday (2018), resource diversification signifies various activities that attempt to reduce organisation instability and uncertainty and achieve long term goals. Holloway (2001) classified these activities into:

- (i.) *unrestricted donor or grant funding* (from private and public sources);
- (ii.) generating new revenue by adopting *entrepreneurial strategies* in the form of non-profit enterprise and diversifying internal funding source; and
- (iii.) *non-financial resources* such as in-kind gifts.

Besides, Damlamian (2006) contends that formalised partnership with other stakeholders including CSOs, funders and corporate organisations could provide some degree of flexibility on how resources could be utilised to offset costs compared to traditional donor funding. Developing a solid positive relationship with private sector does not only yield financial gifting,

but private companies also support CSOs through in-kind donations of goods, providing pro-bono professional services, and having their employees serve as CSO board members. In a similar vein, Pfeffer and Salancik (2003) partly agree with Damlamian (2006) that CSOs should both self-generate revenue and strengthen non-financial collaboration with other stakeholders to address operational dependency and vulnerability.

Consequently, CSOs benefit from revenue diversification which allows them to maximise their income to achieve anticipated objectives. In this light, Hayman (2016) and Carroll and Stater (2009) argue that CSOs that adopt revenue diversification strategy have less volatile funding and greater flexibility of strategic funding options. Therefore, a CSO with diversified income streams could be regarded as more financially stable and viable.

Although, the increased financial stability derived from diversification is at greater risk when controlling different revenue streams (Grasse et al., 2015). Rhoden (2014) convinces that majority of these new diversified avenues increases CSOs' susceptibility to external factors and pressure (Berrett and Holliday, 2018). These external factors could recede existing revenue and result in internal inefficiencies like government control, administrative complexity, goal displacement or shift in mission, revenue volatility, and increased operational costs (Arhin et al., 2018; Mitchell, 2012; Hailey and Salway, 2016). Although, Hayman (2016; pp.676) suggests that 'If diversification happens through a deep review process, that also seeks to build new coalitions... then organisations can potentially make a shift without losing sight of their mission and character.' Also, attaining a satisfactory level of financial sustainability of CSOs demands much more than acquiring resources from diversified sources. It demands improving organizational capacities (Rhoden, 2014).

In summary, there seems to be a consensus as to the importance of revenue diversification. Though, Mitchell (2012) emphasised commercial revenue as the most viable disrupter of CSO's funding diversification, as local CSOs are falling into a "survivalist mode" owing to economic austerity. The next section builds on this argument by examining self-financing CSOs.

2.1.3 Self-Financing CSOs

In the civil society context, opportunities are not in the form of profit-making for the owners but social purpose, 'as any income is re-invested – or ploughed back into the work of the organisation in line with the objectives of the organisation' (Holloway, 2001, p. 36). CSOs are adopting enterprise model as means to benefit from revenue diversification and replace or supplement traditional funding source (Mitchell, 2012; Froelich, 1999; Fowler 2000; Holloway, 2001), by using market strategies and values (Eikenberry and Kluver, 2004). Bowman (2011) states that this alternative funding is unrestricted, more reliable, and independent of the strings often attached to grants and donation.

Several CSOs in Nigeria, including some of those involved in this study, have already adopted a hybrid approach (Adeyeye, 2016, Bell et al., 2010) i.e, 'non-profit in purpose and for-profit in approach, the double bottom line concept' (Alymkulova and Seipulnik 2005, pp. 7) to help them withstand financial crisis and sustain their main social programmes through earned income and the use of donations for ancillary social projects. Some CSOs have transitioned from a purely, traditionally donor-based organisation to 'a viable, market-driven development enterprise' (INTRAC, 2014, pp.12) to generate revenue while others have emerged as a hybrid organisation in Nigeria. These hybrid organisations acquire revenue from selling locally made product, providing fee-based services in education or vocational programmes and consultancy as well as providing cross-subsidisation activities. Although there are positive outlooks on the adoption of an enterprise model towards financial sustainability of CSOs, there are some limitations involved. The contested effects of enterprise model on CSOs include mission drift or goal displacement, increased business cost and risks, limited employee technical capacity, and alienation of some grassroots stakeholders.

A major argument is on the prevalence of development enterprises and their activities. Some researchers argue that hybrid CSOs and social enterprises are prevalent in southern or developing countries (Lepoutre et.al, 2013; Hailey and Salway, 2016; Mair and Marti; 2009). A counterargument is that poor population in developing countries are too concerned with basic needs and may not be able to patronise social enterprise activities, thus, social enterprise

involvement is higher in developed nations with advanced economic development (Lepoutre et.al, 2013 and Frumkin and Keating, 2011). Hayman (2016, p.676) asserts that 'private funding prospects are slim, especially in remote, rural, poor, and volatile parts of countries where private capital is scarce' (p.676). However, Holloway (2001, p.39) argues that the 'poor are not absolutely poor, and that they can pay for some of the costs of services, provided those services are services that they need and want, and provided that they are delivered in ways that they can have some control over'. He went further to contend that the poorest group with no earning potential might not afford the service, 'but there is room for cross-subsidising i.e. charging enough from the poor so that free services can be offered to the poorest' (p.40) and the CSOs can recover their costs. This research contributed to findings on how CSO's enterprise activities impact the poorest and vulnerable groups in Nigeria.

2.2 THEORETICAL APPROACH

Resource Dependence Theory (by Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978)

A theory provides the structure and underpinning for acquiring deep understanding of a novel phenomenon (Silverman, 2017; p. 146). In some of the burgeoning literature and studies on NGO financial strength and sustainability, researchers (Berrett and Holliday, 2018; Mitchell, 2012; Von-Schnurbein and Fritz, 2017; Bowman, 2011; Froelich, 1999; Frumkin and Keating 2011; Eikenberry and Kluver, 2004; Malatesta and Smith, 2014) use RDT for analysing their findings on financial sustainability of CSOs. Drawing on this theory, the researchers argued that there is a correlation between resource dependence and organisations vulnerability, hence, the higher the resource dependence, the higher the vulnerability and vice versa.

RDT is a useful framework to explore the interaction of an organisation with its environment, considering elements like resource "concentration", that is the accessibility of alternative funding sources, and "criticality", a measure of the organisation's capacity to operate without resources. According to Malatesta and Smith (2014), RD theory is based on four principles: (i) organisations require resources for sustenance and to pursue its goals; (ii) organisations could acquire resources from other organisations and its environments; (iii) power and dependency

play important role in examining donor and NGO's relationships; (iv) and balance of power often favour organisation that possesses what other organisations need.

Based on RDT, power and resource dependency are conversely linked (Malatesta and Smith, 2014; Arhin et al., 2018). For instance, the framework has improved the opinion that donors exert domination on CSOs especially when donors determine programme goals as a result of their high dependence on resources (AbouAssi, 2013). Furthermore, RDT shows how high dependence on donor influences organisation management behaviour to leverage on their external environment and adopting strategies such as the formation of a partnership with other stakeholders, co-optation, merging, boards of directors, resource diversification, and concession to donors demands (Pfeffer and Salancik, 2003; Mitchell 2012; Arhin et.al 2018, Eikenberry and Kluver, 2004).

Also, RDT has been put to test to explore the shift from donor-dependence to self-financing, even though 'it is inadequate to examine conditions under which NGOs surrender control to donors' (Mitchell, 2012, pp.3). This study draws on the perspectives from RDT to explore how local CSOs in Nigeria are responding to the changing donor landscape.

2.3 CONCLUSION

Donor aid or grant has been influential in the expansion of the civil society sector. However, the dilemma of reduced and competitive donor-aid funding landscape that CSOs in Nigeria and other low-income countries face has urged local CSOs to adopt revenue generation strategies, especially being business-like to earn income for their social purpose. Also, overwhelming findings from the literature pointed out the limitations and effects of this mechanism on CSOs and their target beneficiaries.

These paradoxes from the pieces of literature reviewed developed into an area of interest for this research. Although, there is inconclusive empirical evidence on whether the shift from donor-dependence to self-sustaining organisation contributes to organisation autonomy. The next chapter presents the methodology of this study.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY AND DATA ANALYSIS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter focuses on the research design and methodology for exploring the financial sustainability strategies of five Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) in Nigeria and to determine the extent of their donor-dependence. Based on the researcher's reflection, complemented by literature, this chapter explicitly discusses the research approaches, identification and recruitment of research population, data collection and validity. Also, ethical issues are the primary component of this chapter discussion.

3.2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research design is the model of investigation created to answer research questions or test the hypothesis of a phenomenon. In this study, the researcher adopted a qualitative method through an exploratory approach to best support the research needs and objectives. The dominance of qualitative research is its capacity to provide deep understanding of the social phenomenon and 'use naturally occurring data to find the sequences ('how') in which participants' meanings ('what') are deployed' (Silverman, 2011, p.17).

Using an exploratory qualitative approach, the researcher gained insight into the phenomenon of CSO financial sustainability. She further analysed the phenomenon using primary data collected using semi-structured interviews and qualitative survey to identify some potential strategies used by these organisations. The interviews were developed to reveal qualitative data rather than quantifiable results. Hence, the interviews included open-ended questions to probe research participants' perceptions and to stimulate in-depth responses from them. In this study, the central research question is exploratory as the researcher has some knowledge and few ideas about the strategies used by CSOs through literature review.

3.3 RESEARCHER'S SUBJECTIVITY AND POSITIONALITY

While conducting the research process and data collection, the researcher was aware of her subjectivity, while considering her personal beliefs and values. The researcher is a Nigerian

postgraduate student who has prior knowledge of the subject matter as she has volunteered in the civil society sector and had struggled to fundraise in both international and local organisations. However, she does not have any direct working experience with the selected CSOs in this study. The challenge to the researcher was to become self-aware, through “self-reflection” (Given, 2008) on how her personal “subjectivity” has driven the overall research processes from data collection to analysis. However, the researcher’s understanding of the phenomenon garnered from both her personal experience and scholarly perspective made it easier to discuss sensitive issues.

3.4 SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Sampling is the process of selecting a limited estimate of cases (“sample”) from an array of units that made up the object of the research (“population”), according to the study criteria (Corbetta, 2003). For the researcher to expand her study findings to the research population, the sample represented a target population defined by a set of systematically employed criteria (Henry, 1990; Salmons, 2012).

This study involves a non-probability and purposive sampling of five CSOs in Nigeria, that serves as a primary data source required to achieve the objective of this study and help address the research questions. The researcher focused on identifying five locally governed CSOs located in South-West Nigeria, with a regional scope and indicating observable features of a sustainable organisation (as described in the literature review chapter) i.e withholding strong financial capacity (Bowman, 2011; Leon, 2001) for more than 10 years (see table 3.1). The data represented the CSOs financial sustainability in Southwest Nigeria, however, the data have a wider generalisability for CSO sector in Nigeria since the participating organisations have programme reach covering all regions of Nigeria.

Table 3.1 CSO Profile

Pseudonym	Year Established	Focus area(s)	Board	Annual budget	No. of employees
Pilot CSO	2010	Skills acquisition and training, livelihood support, Youth empowerment, Education	5	\$50,000	8
CSO-1	1995	Education, Child protection, advocacy, Humanitarianism, Migration, Human rights	8	\$80,000	16
CSO-2	2001	Education, and women empowerment, ICT	6	\$59,500	9
CSO-3	2009	Poverty eradication, Advocacy, Environment, Agriculture	8	\$90,000	14
CSO-4	2007	Education, youth & Women Empowerment, Female education, ICT	7	\$155,000	18
CSO-5	1999	Health, Gender, Humanitarianism, Water and Sanitation	6	\$127,000	21

After verifying that a CSO satisfied the criteria, then its participation in the study was solicited by first cold-emailing the organisation via the email address (usually info@{CSO name}.org) accessible on the website. As the researcher did not have a relationship to most of the organisations sampled for the survey, the response rate for the emails was very low. However, organisations who signified interest in participating in the research were then further contacted via subsequent emails (containing the information sheet and consent form) and phone. Once rapport was established, the individual sample was then selected based on availability and respondent sampling.

The first contacts the researcher had with these organisations were administration officer, marketing officer or volunteers. However, these categories of staff were not suitable for the study purpose. The researcher further identified individual samples (Appendix B) from these

organisations to achieve the research objectives using the following inclusion criteria of one to two key senior management staff (such as CEO, Executive director, Chief Operating Officer or Finance officer) and whose leadership role relates to finance and programmes management. Although, some ethical issues relating to employee’s involvement in employer-based research were considered and discussed in the last section of this chapter.

From the researcher’s observation, organisations are going through an unprecedented time in the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic, as the CSO sector is financially squeezed, scaling back operations and adjusting to the “new normal” of remote working (Bond, 2020). The researcher adjusted its sampling frame due to the issue of access to participants within the organisation by searching for the staff of these identified organisations on social media (LinkedIn). This approach yielded two CSO managers (a programme Director and an Executive Director). The resulting six interviews included a mix of participants with expertise in finance and fundraising, programmes, strategic management and organisation management.

3.5 RESEARCH METHOD AND DATA COLLECTION

This study used an inductive approach in gathering data from the participants’ ideas and perceptions of the phenomenon in the context of a social setting. ‘Qualitative researchers refrain from setting up a theoretically well-defined concept of what they study and from formulating hypotheses in the beginning to test them.’ (Flick, 2018). Data collection was divided into two main phases: Qualitative survey and key participants interviews, through the process of triangulation to establish the validity of findings. According to Silverman (2011, p.369), ‘Triangulation refers to combining multiple theories, methods, observers, and empirical materials, to produce a more accurate, comprehensive and objective representation of the object of the study’.

Figure 3.a: Flow of Data Collection

In this study, the researcher began collecting primary data using survey questionnaire. After analysing the survey data, she then conducted semi-structured interview with the participants. Secondary data include the CSO's information available on the website (programmes report and financial statements).

3.5.1. Qualitative Analysis with Survey

The research used the survey responses as a guide to conducting the interview. The questionnaires included a series of close-ended questions (20 questions, mostly, with multiple-choice answers) that participants responded to within five minutes. It seeks participants' opinions by mapping the questions on two dimensions in line with the research objectives. However, the researcher discovered that some vital questions could not be effectively addressed without a more open-ended question and extended probing. Hence, a follow-up semi-structured interview was to probe the research questions.

3.5.2 Semi-structured Online interviews

A semi-structured interview was employed and appropriate for this study because it is immersive, interactive, flexible and reflexive. It allows the researcher to probe into the financial sustainability strategies of CSOs with one participant at a time while using an interview guide (see Appendix A).

To begin the second stage of data collection, the researcher pretested the interview to determine:

- (1.) interview period (at most 44 minutes);
- (2.) workability of intended questions;
- (3.) and the kind of data that interviews generate.

Firstly, the researcher assumed the role of an interviewee and was interviewed by a friend. The researcher was able to detect questions that were not open-ended such as responding yes and no. And she was able to make changes to the tenses and create an appropriate interview guide for the main study. According to Cohen et al. (2007) pretesting research enables the researcher

to check the completeness and appropriateness of the research instrument. Secondly, the researcher further piloted the research questions with the Founder of CSO-0 (the pilot organisation) which resulted in an additional question to improve data quality.

Figure 3.b: Steps in conducting the pilot study (Majid et al, 2017)

Piloting the interview enables the researcher to have the first-hand experience in facilitating in-depth, semi-structured interview (Majid et al, 2017, p.1076) because as the process progressed, the interview guide quality improved and the researcher's confidence increased. For instance, the research learnt to be careful with leading questions and interrupting participants, she became more relaxed and let the participants talk at their own pace.

Key participants were already identified, and appointments were scheduled for virtual interviews. The semi-structured interview lasted between 29 and 44 minutes and included open-ended questions, accompanied by follow-up queries (why and how) relating to what participants had already said. During the interview, the researcher was able to explore and meander around the topic and delved into totally unforeseen issues. The researcher also ensured that questions were not asked in a way as to evoke pressure that would make the participants worry about

jeopardizing their position and provide socially acceptable answers. By assuring the confidentiality and anonymity, the researcher used prefatory comments like “some CSOs do change their mission in line with funder’s priorities” and then asked the participants about their opinion.

Although the direct conversation and relationship between the researcher and participant occurred virtually through Computer-mediated communications (Salmons, 2012), Microsoft teams. A contentious concern of computer-mediated communications is the building of rapport and that ‘the human qualities so important to interview communications are experienced differently’ (Salmons, 2012), as these qualities provide a certain richness to qualitative data (Iacono et al., 2016). The researcher initiated a connection with participants over time to build rapport by exchanging emails, chatting with them on phone before the interview. Also, Cohen (2007, p. 153) agrees with (Salmons, 2012) on the importance of nonverbal cues, stating that, because of the absence of such cues, computer-mediated communications could ‘undermine the salient conduct of interview, and hence its reliability and validity’. Although, the researcher was still able to observe some nonverbal cues such as the length of participants silence, pitch volume and pace, changes in the tone of voice, facial expressions etc.

After the interview was conducted, the researcher interpreted and transcribed the participants' recorded responses, and sent responses back to the participants in a word document for review and verification of information. There was enough time to re-contact participants who consented to participate in the study. Participants were asked to confirm whether the synthesised results resonated with their experiences and they made changes to the transcripts within 7 days. One participant reconstructed his narrative and added new information to the transcript whereas others made no changes. This process of member checking reduces the potential of the researcher's bias and improves the accuracy of the interview data. (Birt et al., 2016)

3.6 QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

To begin analysing the data, the researcher kept an accurate record of all the data collected in the form of interview transcripts (from audio recording) and notes. She used notes to record her thoughts, key relevant learnings and details for data validity (Nowell et al, 2017). Notes taken

during the interview helped the researcher to formulate new probing questions as the interview moves along. Participants data were saved in separate files and labelled with name, organisation, and date of the interview. Also, the research database was stored in a password protected file in the University of East London “OneDrive” repository to serve as an audit trail (Nowell et al, 2017).

The researcher immersed herself in the data and began interpretation by listening to the recordings repeatedly as advised by Kelly et al. (2006). The data were managed using an Excel spreadsheet to create a chart matrix or mind map. The chart included a summary of the data while retaining the original interpretations and quotations of the participants. By comparing and cross-checking the data from the interview with the survey questionnaire (data triangulation process), the researcher strengthened the data assessment and validity of this research.

Furthermore, the researcher Identified relevant codes emerging across the transcripts. Then she used colours to highlight and organise the codes into sub-themes such as donors, grants, contracts, fee-based services, partnership etc. (see Table 4.1). These sub-themes were then aggregated into categories of best fit and ranked in order of importance. The final stage in the analysis was to link the themes with the literature and the theory to draw conclusion.

3.6.1 GENERATION OF THEMES

After reviewing the interview transcriptions, the researcher undertook an Inductive process of thematic coding to identify findings (codes) emerging across all interview (see table 3.2) while analysing statements and extracting relevant quotes. These findings were categorised into two overarching categories or themes which provided additional valuable insights into the common funding strategies and their effects on the CSOs. The researcher found new important codes along the way, including volunteerism, network participation and community participation, which were categorised under the sub-theme - “social capital”.

Table 3.2: Coding of Participants responses according to theme

Themes or Category	Sub-theme or code families	Participants who responded to questions relating to codes	Frequency of responses relating to themes
1. Key Funding strategies	Donation and Grants (Individual, Corporate & Government funding)	6	61
	Self-financing (Investment, project revenues, membership dues, fee-based products, Government contracts, Consultancy)	6	54
	Social capital (Volunteers, community participation and partnership)	5	23
	Other (board member)	5	9
2. Effect of Financial strategies	Donor relations (Change in priorities & programmatic focus)	6	33
	Exclusion of target beneficiaries	6	22
	Mission drift & legitimacy effects	4	17

3.7 ESTABLISHING QUALITY AND TRUSTWORTHINESS

Research quality is conventionally characterised and assessed by the reliability and validity criteria, which guarantee that the observations from the study reflect the object of study. Although, these concepts are evaluated separately in quantitative research, while in qualitative research, they were replaced with the concept of “trustworthiness”, encompassing the following essential criteria: credibility, dependability, transferability and confirmability (Morse et al., 2002; Elo et al., 2014).

In this research, I probe into the experiences of my study participants for a deeper understanding of the phenomenon and inductively gather valuable data that could be interpreted, transcribed and validated. The researcher employed the following strategies to establish the “trustworthiness” of the study:

(a.) Credibility:

Credibility relates to ensuring that interpretations are accurate by addressing the aspect of truth-value in research findings and ‘testing the findings with the various sources from which the data are drawn’ (Sin, 2010). In this study, the researcher used both pilot interview and member checking strategy (Birt et al, 2016; Korstjens and Moser, 2018), including participants validation of interview transcripts to increase the credibility of data collection.

(b.) Transferability:

Transferability refers to the applicability of the research descriptions and findings in other contexts based on the researcher’s “thick description” (Sin, 2010; Morse et al., 2002) and “purposive sampling” (Given, 2018). The researcher provided evidence that the study could be applicable by detailing information about the context of the CSOs, the sample & the link between the participants to the context studied, and the method for data collection.

(c.) Confirmability

Confirmability is concerned about ensuring that research findings are not ascertained and influenced by the researcher’s biases, motivations and perspectives but derived from the participant’s data (Sin, 2010; Susan and Saltanat, 2016). The researcher maintained a reflexive journal where she reflected on her personal experience practices and recorded issues about sensitive topics that may affect the data gathering in every stage of the study.

3.8 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Various measures were taken to certify research integrity and ethical standards. This research sought and received ethical approval (Appendix C) from the University of East London ethical committee. However, it is important to note that the researcher's application faced challenges that were thoroughly scrutinised by the committee multiple times. Questions were raised around dimensions that the researcher had not considered such as issues of adequacy of the informed consent and protection of participants privacy, sampling strategies, and the minimisation of risks to participants. The researcher was happy to consider feedback and modify the research approach in the most ethical form. Also, the research committee advice was instrumental in facilitating the overall study.

The researcher was aware of the risks of employer-based research, including how employer-employee recruitment may affect the potential research findings which may result from the possibility of undue influence (Resnik, 2016). In this study, a participant was recruited by the CEO of CSO-3. However, the researcher mitigated any issues of coercion and influence by ensuring that the CEO consented to select only employees who voluntarily decide to participate in the research. Also, the informed consent document indicated that the employee's decision to participate should not affect his employment status, performance evaluation or benefit. The potential participant was contacted directly by the researcher to provide the informed consent document and reassured the employee that his job will not be compromised by non-participation. Also, the employee was informed that he can withdraw his participation at any time and have the right not to answer some questions.

Also, the researcher ensured that no harm or adverse consequences will come to the participants as a result of their participation in the study by discerning the information to be reported and what should not be publicly disclosed and ensuring that anonymity and confidentiality measures are enforced.

3.9 CONCLUSION

This chapter has provided justifications for the research methodology processes used in this study. It described the nature of the study as being exploratory and inductive, thus enabling the researchers to learn more about the research phenomenon. Throughout the data collection and analysis processes, the researcher remained reflexive of her personal biases, questioned her motivations and assumptions about the phenomenon.

Using an inductive thematic analysis approach to formulate and organize codes into themes. The two important themes that emerged from the data analysis will be discussed extensively in the next two chapters.

CHAPTER FOUR THEMATIC FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION I: CSO FINANCIAL STRATEGIES

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the key findings under the first identified theme – CSO financial strategies. These findings will be evaluated and discussed explicitly based on the following research questions:

Research Question 1: *What strategies are particularly contributing to the financial sustainability of local CSOs in Nigeria?*

Research Question 2: *What are the factors that influence the local CSOs' adoption of diversified revenue streams?*

Research Question 3: *How do donors support the financial sustainability of CSOs?*

The researcher has approached the analysis and discussion of findings with brief response descriptions of each research question.

4.2 WHAT STRATEGIES ARE PARTICULARLY CONTRIBUTING TO THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF LOCAL CSOS IN NIGERIA?

Participants selected relevant sustainability strategies in the survey. To investigate further, the researcher assessed the organisations' levels of funding, budgets and discussed extensively on resource diversification, which then revealed additional funding models during the interview. For example, all the six participants mentioned how their organisations have generated income through commercial means, however, this contradicted the earlier survey result (fig.4.a) where two participants selected the "fee-for-service" strategy. This indicates the drawback of accuracy and validity when using survey methodology (Kelley et al., 2003; Glasow, 2005) as respondents do not 'provide 100% rational responses to your questionnaire' (Ramshaw, 2020).

Figure 4.a: Participants survey response to question on funding strategies

Analysis of the survey results in combination with the interviews with participants showed that the CSOs in general exhibits more similarities than differences with regards to funding diversification strategies. All the CSOs reported that they have developed diverse funding base over the last 10 years. Subsequently, figure 4.b showed that five participants reported Increased funding while one organisation reported that funding has remained the same over the last five years of operation.

Over the last 5 years has there been any changes in funding to the organisation
6 responses

Figure 4.b: Participants survey response to question on funding changes

The identified funding models were classified into four – Donation and grants, Government funding, Self-financing and Social Capital.

4.2.1 DONATIONS AND GRANTS

The findings indicated that the participating CSOs continue to be largely reliant on external sources to finance their major activities. Grants and donations were viewed as the most

dependable source of income. Four CSOs reported that they received most of their funding from international donors such as multilateral organisations, international religious organisations, foreign government agencies among others. While the other CSO reported receiving their major donations from local funders. Nonetheless, the fact that most of the funding was from international donors is a confirmation of information cited in the USAID sustainability Index Nigeria report (2019).

The participants provided a list of donors (see table 4.1) from which they have received funding in the last 10 years.

Table 4.1: Interviews with sample CSOs revealed donors in the last 10 years to include:

Types of Donors	Examples of specific Donors
1. Foreign Government Donor Agencies	United States of America Embassy, DFID, Australian Embassy, USAID, German Embassy, USAID
2. International Institutions	European Union, UNICEF, UNDP, UNESCO, WHO, World Bank, United Nations Population fund
3. International NGOs or Grant-making organisations	Save the children, Rotary club, African development foundation, Global Fund for Children, African women development fund, Global Fund for Women, Globalgiving, Oxfam International, Segal family foundation, Dining for Women,
4. International Corporate foundations	Qatar Foundation, Google foundation, Ford Foundation, The Rockefeller Foundation, Echoing Green Foundation, Varkey foundation, Adobe foundation, MacArthur Foundation, Mastercard foundation, Clinton Foundation, Western Union foundation
5. Local grant-making foundations	Dangote Foundation, ACT foundation, MTN foundations, Danjuma foundation, Tony Elumelu Foundation, Toyin Saraki's Wellbeing Foundation, Mo Ibrahim foundation,
6. Local corporate sponsorships	Banks (Guaranty Trust Bank, United Bank of Africa, Union Bank, Access Bank), Oil & Gas companies (Chevron, Exxon Mobil, Oando), Food & Beverage companies (Coca-cola, Cadbury, Nestle), Telecommunications (MTN Nigeria, Globacom, Airtel Nigeria and 9Mobile)
7. Individual donation	Philanthropist, Parents of program beneficiaries, School owners, board members, friends of the organisation and through online Crowdfunding

The researcher did not only learn about existing donors that support development work in Nigeria but also found out that the participants leverage on these donors to acquire new ones.

All participants mentioned that their organisations have a fundraising plan and committee. The Head of grants and communication of CSO-3 explained how he often took a strategic approach in the identification of grant opportunities:

We always look out for opportunities online which are in the form of call for proposal...every quarter I develop grant calendar to include lists of potential grants...I check the grant criteria to ensure that we are compliant and eligible and we begin to apply for the grant as soon as possible.

Also, C-5 pointed out that donors sometimes contact them to request for proposals or apply for their grant “When donors reach out to us, we know we have a greater chance of being funded”.

Another important strategy identified under “Donation and Grant” theme is Individual donation. All participants mentioned how individual donations have contributed to financial sustainability. This form of donation is more regular but relatively small. Support from individuals, as C-5 said, “people who believe in our organisation” has been a reliable source for CSOs funding to achieve long-term sustainability.

CSOs have been able to raise support from individuals through online and organising events:

- (i.) **Online Crowdfunding** emerged as a new sub-theme which is regarded as a valuable and preferred source of individual donations for all participants. C-3 commented that “we also get donations from public funding (crowdfunding)...we partner with platforms that verify us, such as #GivingTuesday”. CSOs are leveraging on online and social media network (Tonetti, 2019) to fundraise using donation-enable platforms like Facebook, Crowdwise, GoFundMe and Indiegogo. This study showed how technology is improving CSOs fundraising efforts, however, the question that remained unanswered is to what extent do CSOs maintain relationship with online donors. This is a particularly interesting finding which could be further studied to identify best practices that organizations use to optimize donor relation and retention efforts.

(ii.) **Fundraising events** such as gala dinners, dance marathon, sports tournament and shows, are used for mobilising individual donations.

The reoccurring emphasis on Individual donation depicted that it contributed in no small measure to financial sustainability. This is one of the options proffered by Pfeffer and Salancik for local organisations to reduce external dependencies (Hillman et al., 2019).

4.2.2 NATIONAL GOVERNMENT FUNDING (GRANT)

In this study, all participants view national government contribution as being their least dependable source of revenue. “We wish there are enough government financial assistance”, C-5 complained. Only C-2 reported having received a grant from the government (see fig. 3), while other participants described the struggle of accessing limited government funds. However, C-1, C-4, and C-6 pointed out that a formalised partnership with the government was more important than getting funding for their sustainability.

Figure 4.c: Participants survey response to government funding

4.2.3 SOCIAL CAPITAL

A further novel finding from the analysis was that social capital is a crucial strategy that has often been overlooked. All participants highlighted that they have relied on one or more of the following mechanisms especially when they are facing financial crises or have limited access to donors:

Community participation: CSO-5 worked with local community members to design health project, addressing the major areas of needs identified in the consultation stage and then implemented the project in collaboration with the community:

We have had cases where community members contribute both financial and non-financial resources. In 2015, the Oba (the king) of Elegushi gave us a plot of land to build a community health centre which also serves as our office till today.

Other researchers have proven that community participation contributes greatly to the sustainability and effectiveness of development projects (Chambers, 1994; Dale, 2004; Reed, 2008) which in turn strengthen communities' ownership. Using this finding, it is quite interesting to note that community participation also contributes to organisational sustainability, as C-6 stated, "We no longer have to worry about office space and rent".

Volunteer support: All participants acknowledged the role volunteers play in contributing to reducing financial costs, as C-6 commented that:

On several occasions, we have used both local and international volunteers to occupy some intermediate roles within the organisation and to implement projects. They (volunteers) have relieved my organisation from paying salary or extra cost of paying consultant thousands of naira.

Network participation: Partnership was also referenced as another important mechanism for creating social capital. For example, C-4 mentioned how partnership and network support has helped the organisation to navigate complex bureaucratic processes associated with funding applications, especially for large donors, -"By collaborating with other organisations and donors and being part of a network has resulted to direct funding opportunities on multiple occasions."

Regardless of the reports that reduction in funding landscape is resulting in increased competition amongst CSOs (Arhin et al., 2018; Parks, 2008; Nunnenkamp & Ohler, 2010), this research finding revealed the opposite. CSOs were entering alliances as a strategic response to the constant fluctuations in funding landscape and to 'gain power over resource providers' (Hillman et al., 2009, p.1407). This finding is quite surprising and holds a depth of potential as the levels of cooperation between these organisations can be further explored.

Also, with regards to power, this study found CSOs gain collective power over donors through network partnership. The RD theory emphasises the importance of partnership (merger), as a strategic approach to reduce competition and encourage interdependence (Damlamian, 2006; Hillman et al., 2009).

4.2.4 SELF-FINANCING

The second most important funding for these CSOs is income that these organisations earn through the sales of goods and service, which provided a greater cushion for financial uncertainties (Fowler, 2000; Froelich, 1999; Alymkulova and Seipulnik, 2005; Holloway, 2001;) and serve as a buffer between projects and operations (Bowman, 2011). This commercial intervention involves a cost-recovery component through fee-for-service, where beneficiaries pay to get value. For example, CSO-2 is an education NGO that "...run paid summer STEM Camps for training children in STEM programmes...generating revenue this way has reduced reliance on donors".

In this study, the participants' common self-financing activities fall under training, consultancy, microfinance and retail (see table 4.c).

Table 4.2: Examples of Earned-Income Activities

Earned Income Category	Specific Activities	Organisation
Education and Vocational training	Training, recruitment and placement	CSO-1, CSO-2, CSO-3, and CSO-4
Consultancy and Contract	Corporate social responsibility (CSR), Government contract, M&E and project consulting	CSO-1, CSO-2 and CSO-4
Microfinance	Loan	CSO-3 and CSO-4
Rent	Office space, equipment and other assets	CSO-1, CSO-2, CSO-3, CSO-4 and CSO-5
Product development and retail	Software products (website and mobile app), Training kits, handicrafts, farming and fishery produce, Job shadowing,	CSO-1, CSO-2, CSO-3, and CSO-4
Member dues	Board members fees	CSO-1, CSO-4

This revenue diversification strategy was a focal point and considered important for the five participating organisations to help mitigate donor dependence and maintain autonomy (Fowler, 2000; Mitchell, 2012). The diversification paradigm is well-grounded in the RDT, which according to Pfeffer and Salancik (2003) the theory explained the change in the organisation’s behaviour (Werner, 2008) to adopt business strategy because they are wary of the power of external actors (donors) and as a means to increase their power or autonomy.

4.2.5 BOARD RESOURCE PROVISION

All participants revealed how resources provided by the board of directors’ have been instrumental to their organizational sustainability. When asked whether board contributes financially to the organisation, C-4 said, *“our board members contribute at least \$5000 annually, from their pocket (personal contribution)”*.

The finding also showed that board provide leadership in fundraising by mobilizing resources from network contribution (family, friends and professional network), facilitating partnership as well as providing expert guidance and advice, for example, *“a lot of our donors are from the board*

network..two of our board members lead the grant and fundraising committee...they provide feedback and make final decisions on written proposals and grant applications”.

In support of RDT proposition, this study also recognises board as a provider of critical resources and observable strategy aimed at ‘reducing uncertainty and managing the demands of the environment’ (Werner, 2008, p. 15)

4.3 WHAT ARE THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE LOCAL CSOS’ ADOPTION OF DIVERSIFIED REVENUE STREAMS?

DWINDLING DONOR FUNDING

Due to the size of the research sample, one factor was identified in this study. The absolute inference drawn from the participant data was the reduction and inaccessibility of international donor funding. Data gathered shows that donor support for the analysed sample has decreased progressively in the last 7 years. For example, C-6 expressed her view that “we are starting to see a reduction in the number of grants available for health programmes every year”. The analysis reflected that participants adopted commercial strategy between the year 2012 and 2016 and reported that those were the critical times they experienced financial crises the most. This is consistent with what has been found in previous studies in East and West Africa (Arhin, 2018; Beyene, 2014; Gitonga, 2018; Omeri, 2015). Overall, what is evident from this finding is the critical need to find alternative means of getting returns on their services through cost recovery of operational costs.

4.4 HOW DO DONORS SUPPORT THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF CSOS?

All participating CSOs mentioned that organisational sustainability is a secondary concern for donors. Donor supports are more concentrated on projects that have positive impacts. For example, C-3 said, “*Funders are not interested in building our institutional capacity to become sustainable...even though they ask us for our sustainability plan*”.

However, this study shows that unrestricted funding and training has been instrumental in the organisation’s financial sustainability.

4.4.1 Unrestricted Core Funding:

Participants emphasised that few funders integrate sustainability support into project grants and mentioned critical points in their history during which they had received unrestricted funding usually between 3-7% of the total fund which has contributed to sustainability. The importance of providing unrestricted funding support to CSOs are well documented by McCray (2015), and CSOs have used this unrestricted fund to cover operational costs like overhead, rent, and equipment. It could be pointed out that this study reflected that when CSOs have enough unrestricted core funding, their fundraising effort could be reduced, thus, it allows CSOs to concentrate on their development work.

4.4.2 Capacity-Building

Asides from the provision of financial resources, the participants highlighted other means that donors have supported the organisation such as providing training in the form of capacity building. However, the training is tailored to improving project output rather than fundraising strategies of the organisation. C-1 shared her opinion that capacity building is “more of project management training than skills-building for organisational development”. This view was also echoed by Bell et al. (2010) and Bokoff et al. (2015). They argued that capacity-building support rarely equates with financial sustainability.

However, it is worth noting that the finding reflected how CSO leaders are thinking entrepreneurially while leveraging on the skills from the capacity building training to earn revenue. C-2 noted that “I was trained by Ford Foundation and even got certification...we now provide consultancy service in Monitoring and Evaluation”. Therefore, CSOs are leveraging the technical skills of their staff to earn income such as providing training and consultancy services in their areas of specialization.

4.5 CONCLUSION

This chapter has been able to provide insights into three research questions about the key funding strategies contributing to financial sustainability when CSOs are struggling to access foreign donations and grants. The two most important funding streams for the participants include donation and earned-income. The discoveries of this study contributed to the literature review, except for the exceptional findings on online crowdfunding, and the social capital. Also, the findings revealed how CSOs have leveraged on additional donor support to achieve sustainability such as the skills acquired from capacity building training. The next chapter will look into the effects of these strategies on the organisation.

CHAPTER FIVE

THEMATIC FINDING AND DISCUSSION II: DONOR INFLUENCE AND EFFECT OF ALTERNATIVE FUNDING

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the second key thematic findings about the influence of resource mobilisation on local CSOs in Nigeria. The two most important funding strategies (donations and earned income) of the organisations will be further analysed to determine the external control concerned with Resource dependence theory (RDT). 'RDT recognizes the influence of external factors on organisational behaviour' (Hillman et al., 2009, pp.1404).

This chapter will therefore answer the following research questions:

Research Question 4: What evidence is there of donor power being exerted on CSOs?

Research Question 5: What are the effects of these strategies on the CSO's mission and programs?

5. 2 WHAT EVIDENCE IS THERE OF DONOR POWER BEING EXERTED ON CSOS?

The interviews highlighted participants' perceptions of donor's strong influence on their organisation as they almost depend entirely on donor funding for viability.

5.2.1 Control of Funding

The control of funding was the most common mechanism identified in this study. All participants pointed out that donors decide grant amount and timeframe of funding availability, which invariably determine CSOs' project planning and implementation. An example was shared by the participant from CSO-5:

There was an outbreak of Lassa fever in Ondo state last year and we needed additional funding...we reached out to X (donor), but we received an email saying that their funding cycle is closed for the year.

This shows how the donor's rigid funding timeframe impact development project. This external control over the flow of resources threatens local CSO's potential at a point in time. As Pfeffer

and Salancik (2003) postulated that when organisations depend on unstable external environment, problems arise.

Also, donors have restrictive conditions and cumbersome funding pattern, mostly in multiple tranches. As C-2 commented that:

Sometimes we receive funding...where the donor provides grants to us in stages or arrears...even when we receive the fund, we encounter long delay and audit than expected before we can use the grant.

Multi-tranche funding tends to affect CSOs, especially those with insufficient working capital to offset unanticipated project expenses. Donor disbursement lag may result in slow project implementation (Khan et al., 2017; Milton, 2008). To avoid delay in project implementation or mitigate donor slow or bureaucratic funding disbursement procedures, Pfeffer and Salancik (2003) recommend that CSOs develop diverse funding base outside the control of external actors. It is therefore apparent that CSOs with earned income can manage cash flow while waiting for donor disbursement and handling arrear contributions (Karlstedt et al., 2015).

5.2.2 Donor's funding priorities and interest:

Another interesting finding was the shift in international donors' priorities which reflected greater influence on CSOs. Availability of funding often dictates which development problem are placed high on national agenda and the types of programmes selected to address the problem. For example, CSO-6 which focused on health described how donors prioritised and influenced certain disease-specific programmes while neglecting other important areas, specifically when they focus on pre-determined national goals.

We focused only on maternal and child health during our first five years of operation...we stopped getting enough funding and we had to diversify to WASH (Water, Sanitation and Hygiene). In doing so, we did not entirely change our programme but sort of modified it, so we take strategic approach in applying for donor fundings available in any those areas.

This finding is similar to Morfit (2011) study in Malawi where donor prioritised HIV/AIDS for two decades, resulting in the disappearance of other priorities.

As at the time of the interview, the C-6 mentioned that the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) was prioritised and placed high on the national agenda, so CSOs are adjusting their case for support to include new COVID-related programs. This finding indicated that CSOs are highly respondent to the interests of donors while overlooking the needs or priorities of their intended beneficiaries.

To buttress this point, C-2 described and emphasised how CSOs are navigating between pragmatic approaches which are contingent upon the relationship with donors, - “You really need to nurture foreign donors...whenever their priorities changed, negotiate with them by asking how your organisation can adapt”. C-2 further elucidated that their relationship with donors is unequal and they are obliged to donor’s demand. This is in line with Hulme and Edwards (1997, p.54) arguments that donor-CSO relationship could be regarded as ‘bargaining and negotiation, although times marked by coercion’.

Hence, this trend provokes the researcher’s perceptions that CSOs actions are highly driven by donor’s priorities and interest. As CSOs are urged to “follow the money” by permitting donors to impose programme scope (Viravaidya and Hayssen, 2001).

5.2.3 Beneficiary accountability

Participants mentioned how they have felt pressured to meet donor’s set metrics. C-2 highlighted how they have to show the intended impact of the fund in the project proposal, “donors want to know how much it will cost to impact a beneficiary, they want to quantify impact per every naira spent”. Another example was when CSO-4 committed to training 1000 Teachers in a 1-year project cycle, but they did not meet the number at the end of the project, “according to our M&E officer, we trained about 985 teachers”. She pointed out how they came up with a number a little above 1000 to have a chance of being funded in the future. This is a perfect situation where CSOs

feel uncomfortable to report the actual result to donors for fear that an apparent failure could affect future funding.

Regarding performance measurement, Ebrahim (2003, p.818) states that donors stringent data assessment requirement could lead “NGOs to exaggerate successes, while discouraging them from revealing and closely scrutinizing their mistakes”. Also, it shows the implication of asymmetric donor-CSO relationship, as the pressure CSOs face to be accountable “upward” to maintain reputation could undermine their credibility and legitimacy (Banks et al., 2014; Ebrahim, 2003). However, Anderson (2014) thinks that both upward and downward accountabilities are important to validate CSOs effectiveness in development.

5.3 WHAT ARE THE EFFECTS OF THE REVENUE GENERATING STRATEGY ON THE CSO’S MISSION AND PROGRAMS?

5.3.1 Mission Drift Effect

The researcher found out that most CSOs mission statements have changed when broadening their revenue base in the last 10 years. For example, CSO-1 started as an advocacy organisation that promotes the social inclusion of street children. The shift occurred when the organisation received a 2-year grant from UNICEF to implement grassroots project on child education and protection. CSO-1 have been prioritising service provision in education over advocacy since then. Therefore, it is clear that external influence is shifting CSOs away from their grassroots advocacy orientation to service provision (Banks et al., 2014). This is also a concern of the RDT as CSOs adapt to the inevitable shift in donor priorities and ‘then find ways to re-invent themselves to be more attractive to donors’ (Parks, 2008).

Similarly, CSO-4, a women empowerment organisation changed its mission in 2017 when it launched its enterprise initiative, girls coding Bootcamp that charges a fee for its course and accommodates about 15% of boys’ participation. C-5 said,

We work with women, so recently in our “X” programme, we had to allow boys in the course of the program, although we ensure that women are fully involved.

These findings revealed how mission is linked to CSO's funding streams by unfolding situations about their search for financial sustainability.

5.3.2 Issue of Legitimacy

CSOs in this study face the issue of legitimacy in their community when they were placing fees on their programmes. For example, the Programme Director of CSO-2 revealed how someone accused his organisation of being too business-oriented, "we had simply told him that our programme costs 15,000 Naira...his response was outrageous, he said 'but you people call yourself NGO and you still want us to pay'".

Here, the CSO's core role was blurred across its donor-driven activities and its business fee-based services. This suggests that the community have a misconception about CSOs with business model as they view them as organisations that no longer represent civil society and conform to their socially prescribed role, whether the 'business activity is in-line with the CSO's mission or not' (Banks et al., 2014). It is therefore interesting that within this context, the organisation was criticised for its dual role of CSO and commercial entity.

5.3.3 Exclusion of specific groups

Another promising finding is that some groups were unintendedly neglected or disregarded to participate in services that are open to others. When asked how benefits from their fee-based programmes trickle down to the poorest group, a common response from the participants is that their enterprise initiatives were not set up for the poorest, even though their customers are still poor, they set the price at a level affordable to the poor. For example, CSO-3 highlighted that "our microcredit programme provides free training to rural farmers but do not provide credit and loan incentives to those farmers who are not guaranteed for repayment". Therefore, most of the extreme poor farmers were excluded from the service. The poor seem to benefit to a greater extent than the poorest, by having access to assets. This particular finding supplements other studies' (Buckland, 2004; Holloway, 2001; Gibson, 1993) results that reflect how CSOs practices further marginalise the poorest group and vulnerable populations.

Although, Chief Operating Officer of CSO-4 acknowledged that the organisation provides limited scholarship or free participation to young women from low-income families:

Our fee-based training programmes target people who have the resource capacity and could afford our fees such as middle-income earners. However, we provide scholarship slots for our primary stakeholders...we also have a model called “pay-it-back”, this way we train the women for free, connect them to job and then they pay back (the training fee) later.

This finding is similar to Holloway’s (2001, p.5) study that organisations use “cross-subsiding i.e ‘enough income is earned to offer free services to a small number of absolutely poor’.

5.4 CONCLUSION

Donor’s influence on CSOs was highlighted strongly in the interviews which indicates that the propositions of the RDT are relevant on these organisations. As a result, these organisations were willing to “dance to the tune” of the donors so that they can have access to continuous funding. Also, the findings presented in this chapter suggests that CSOs understudy struggle to maintain a relationship with their target beneficiaries and maintain their mission while managing their enterprise activities.

CHAPTER SIX

OVERALL DISCUSSION, RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides an overview of the study on CSO financial sustainability in South-West, Nigeria. Thereafter, it presents its contribution to wider academia literature and provides recommendations based on the findings. It also presents the research limitations and suggested areas for future research that would be relevant to the body of knowledge about CSO financial sustainability.

6.2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

This is a postgraduate dissertation involving comprehensive study on the phenomenon of financial sustainability of local CSOs in Nigeria. This research used qualitative method to collect primary data through survey questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, while assessing five local CSOs founded between the year 1999 and 2007 in Nigeria. The researcher used an inductive thematic coding approach to categorise the research findings into two key themes:

- (i.) Funding Strategies
- (ii.) Effect and Influence of funding strategies

To put the discussion into perspective, the findings were further analysed at two different levels: the civil society sector and organisation.

At the organisation level, CSOs in Nigeria are struggling to maintain operation and deliver services in a period of reduced foreign funding. A few CSOs have acquired government funding (including contracts) while the majority are leveraging social capital, board of director and adopting commercial strategy, which has various consequences. This study confirms the views of researchers (Hailey and Salway, 2016; Carroll and Stater, 2009) that organisations need to strategically diversify their funding base in response to external pressures. Although, this study shows that the LCSOs in Nigeria are still very much dependent on donor, as donation and grant occupies between 50-55% of their total annual funding. Also, social capitals are usually in the form of non-financial support. However, the magnitude or valuation of in-kind donation is hard

to gauge accurately and requires careful analysis for CSO financial reporting. Many investigative articles (including Brenner, 2013; Klopper, 2019) have questioned the valuation of in-kind donation per standard accounting principles to ensure values are not inflated.

Also, it is noteworthy that CSOs' commercial activities also garner more donor support as it reassures donors that CSOs and their project can be sustained after short-term donor support. As C-4 substantiated the claim that donors asked for their long-term sustainability plan in proposals, "we embed revenue-generating component in our project design". This finding attests Defourny and Nyssens (2010) study but contradicts Young (1998) assertion that commercial activities 'undermine the confidence of donors or otherwise discourages giving' (p.279)

On the other hand, the findings at the Civil society sector level have revealed how the sector in developing countries like Nigeria has evolved in scope and scale (CIVICUS, 2018) in a time when foreign aid is diminishing and there is a drastic cut in government grants. Firstly, the civil society sector which was traditionally characterised and promoted by international aid has begun to change. Alternative funding models have complemented the dominant one. New organisational and business models are emerging, for example, the commercialisation of staff skills. Secondly, technology innovation is disrupting the sector and has opened new opportunities to organize fundraising effort, re-engineer fundraising model and 'access funding from multitude of private resources' (Williams, 2018). Thirdly, the sector has become a highly competitive environment and local CSOs are under pressure to increasingly embrace partnership or merger with both the private sector and other CSOs. Finally, it could be concluded that there has been a paradigm shift in Civil society in developing countries like Nigeria towards financial sustainability.

Consequently, the revenue generation processes transform the donor-CSO-beneficiary relationship and CSOs' behaviour. Because of high dependence, donors exert operational influence on CSOs (AbouAssi, 2013) and 'as priorities move to new areas, the power relations between donors and their NGO grantees become increasingly asymmetric' (Parks, 2008, p.12). When CSOs increased their funding base without compromising their mission, they achieve autonomy and become accountable to the people they serve (beneficiaries or clients). This led to the reversal of the donor-CSO-beneficiary relationship as described by Ebrahim (2003) and

Banks et al. (2014). Although, there are concerns that CSOs drive for lucrativeness undermines their humanitarian values, legitimacy and transparency. This study showed that CSOs with earned income strategies may be at the risk of blurring or losing their reputation in the sector, as this strategy creates tension with their mission and jeopardise their legitimacy (Weisbrod, 2004).

6.3 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS

This research has hitherto contributed value to academic debates and literature on financial sustainability, revenue diversification, social enterprise, and donor-CSO relations. While some of the findings from this research coincided with existing literature on the research phenomenon, there are notable divergences, such as the commercialisation of staff skills and online crowdfunding. Also, this study constitutes the contributions to the framework of resource dependence theory (RDT).

Moreover, this research provides a country-specific perspective from a developing country, which is an added value to the literature (Mitchell, 2012; Eikenberry and Kluver, 2004; Malatesta and Smith, 2014; Frumkin et al., 2011) covering developed countries. In this regard, this research has contributed to linking North and South academic and scientific research on CSO financial sustainability, specifically for hybrid CSOs.

6.4 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Despite the novel findings derived from the study, it has some limitations. The data collection was restricted to a small sample size of only five organisations founded for over ten years in Nigeria, considering that the country has over 92,000 registered CSOs (Yerima, 2017). Therefore, the limitations of this research give room for other researchers to further investigate the phenomenon. The following has been identified as possible future research areas:

- (i.) Online Crowdfunding: To what extent do CSOs maintain relationship with online donors. How do CSOs minimize the issue of perception of social media exploitation?
- (ii.) Network Partnership: Determination of levels of cooperation between local CSOs and other organisation

More investigation is required to answer these critical questions, within the context of a developing country. Qualitative research will be valuable in this regard.

6.5 RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this master's dissertation project has revealed the important funding strategies used by local CSOs in Nigeria to mitigate the change in donor's funding landscape and achieve autonomy. It also revealed how the revenue streams have impacted the organisations' behaviour.

The following recommendations are supported by the findings:

1. CSOs can push for policies that will be beneficial in self-financing and fundraising.
2. Donors to build in much greater flexibility to earmarked funds to enable reallocation of funds in the case of CSOs' changing needs and to enable no-cost extensions.
3. Donors to provide small grants to assist CSOs in bolstering their capacity to do fundraising and income-generating activities.

I hope the policy implications and recommendations would raise the awareness of development actors and researchers about local CSOs financial sustainability.

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APPENDIX A

SAMPLE INTERVIEW GUIDE

RESEARCH TOPIC: Financial Sustainability: Understanding Local CSO Strategies to Reduce Donor Dependence in South West Nigeria

RESEARCH CENTRAL QUESTION: What strategies are particularly contributing to the financial sustainability of local CSOs in Nigeria?

State Name of Organisations:

State your position in the organisation:

Organisation founding year:

INTERVIEW SCHEDULED FOR NGO LEADERS

Examine local CSOs unrestricted funding strategies to increase revenue.

In general, how would you define financial sustainability?

Local and international Donor support

Can you tell me about your organisation donors?

How often does the organisation receive donor funding in a year?

How do you explain donor contribution to your organisational sustainability?

How would you describe your organisation's relationship with donors?

Alternative funding

Can you remember a period in the past 10 years, when you had explored other revenue sources?

How do you explain your organisation decision in considering these alternative funding strategies?

Can you tell me more about other strategies contributing to your organisation's sustainability?

Examine organisation management and technical capacity towards CSO's financial sustainability

Leadership and Management:

Who are the significant people responsible for ensuring that the organisation is financially sound and sustainable?

How do you describe their contribution to the organisation financial sustainability?

Understand the effects of these strategies on their mission, autonomy, sustainability and management practices

You provided a list of strategies that you adopted for financial sustainability.

Has there been any changes in the nature of development programmes implemented based on the strategies?

How have your interactions with donors impacted implementation of programmes?

Tell me about a situation when your organisation considered changing its mission?

How do you design social enterprise programmes to reach poor group?

APPENDIX B: INDIVIDUAL SAMPLE

Org. Pseudonym	Interviewee ID	Gender	Position	Expertise
Pilot CSO	C0	Male	Founder	Strategic management, board management, Finance and fundraising, Programme development, Stakeholder management
CSO-1	C1	Male	CEO	Strategic management, Board relation, Fundraising, organisation management
CSO-2	C2	Male	Programmes Director	Programmes design, Fundraising, Monitoring and Evaluation, Stakeholder management
CSO-3	C3	Male	Head of Grant and Communication	Fundraising, Financial management, relationship or partnership development, grant-writing
CSO-4	C4	Female	Executive Director	Organisational leadership, Fundraising, partnership development, programmes management, strategic management
	C5	Female	Chief Operating Officer	Organisational leadership, Stakeholder management, financial management
CSO-5	C6	Male	Founder & CEO	Board leadership, strategic management, Fundraising,

APPENDIX C: INFORMATION SHEET

University of
East London

Pioneering Futures Since 1898

Consent to Participate in a Research Study

The purpose of this letter is to provide you with the information that you need to consider in deciding whether to participate in this study.

Project Title

CSOs Financial Sustainability in South-west, Nigeria: What can be learnt in terms of good practices?

Project Description

This study is about assessing best financial practices of local CSOs in Nigeria towards organisational sustainability and effectiveness. Also, it will assess the effect of funding diversification on the financial sustainability of CSO and program design for the poorest group.

Participants will complete a 3-minute survey and be interviewed for a period of approximately 45 minutes. The probability of harm/discomfort anticipated as a result of participating in this study are not greater than those ordinarily encountered in daily life.

Confidentiality of the Data

Interviews and surveys will be anonymised. However, there may be legal limitations to the level of confidentiality that can be offered where the sample size is small or where focus groups are conducted, and participants can self-identify themselves or others. Participants' confidentiality will be maintained unless a disclosure is made that indicates that the participant or someone else is at serious risk of harm. Interviews will be recorded with your permission and uploaded to 'OneDrive' which only the researchers can access. There they will be stored in password protected files only accessible to the researchers. All identifiable personal data will be stored separately from the recordings to protect participants' confidentiality. No personal data will be kept for longer than the research period and all non-anonymised personal data will be destroyed at the end of the research period.

Location

The research will be carried out online.

Remuneration

Participants will not receive payment.

Disclaimer

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you are free to withdraw at any time during the research. Should you choose to withdraw from the programme you may do so without disadvantage to yourself and without any obligation to give a reason. Please note that your data can be withdrawn up to the point of data analysis – after this point it may not be possible.

University Research Ethics Sub-Committee

If you have any concerns regarding the conduct of the research in which you are being asked to participate, please contact:

**Catherine Hitchens, Research Integrity and Ethics Manager, Graduate School, EB 1.43
University of East London, Docklands Campus, London E16 2RD
Email: researchethics@uel.ac.uk**

APPENDIX D:

Consent to Participate in a Program Involving the Use of Human Participants.

Project Title

CSOs Financial Sustainability in South-west, Nigeria: What can be learnt in terms of good practices?

Researcher

Tolulope Owajoba
NGO and Development management
Faculty of Social Science
University of East London,
United Kingdom
Email: u1928125@uel.ac.uk

Please tick as appropriate:

	YES	NO
I have read the information leaflet relating to the above program of research in which I have been asked to participate and have been given a copy to keep. The nature and purposes of the research have been explained to me, and I have had the opportunity to discuss the details and ask questions about this information. I understand what is being proposed and the procedures in which I will be involved have been explained to me.		
I understand that my participation may be audio recorded and I consent to this.		
I understand that my involvement in this study, and particular data from this research, will remain strictly confidential as far as possible. Only the researchers involved in the study will have access to the data. <i>(Please see below)</i>		
I understand that maintaining strict confidentiality is subject to the following limitations: Interviews and surveys will be anonymized. However, there may be legal limitations to the level of confidentiality that can be offered where the sample size is small and participants can self-identify themselves or others. Where possible, participants' confidentiality will be maintained unless a disclosure is made that indicates that the participant or someone else is at serious risk of harm.		
I understand that anonymized quotes will be used in presentations and publications.		
I understand that I will not have the option to be named in publications.		
I understand that research findings will be disseminated via presentations and academic publications.		
I understand that the data may be used by research team in future research that goes beyond the life of this project.		
I understand that I may be contacted by the research team for participation in future projects.		

It has been explained to me what will happen once the program has been completed.		
I understand that my participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and I am free to withdraw at any time during the research without disadvantage to myself and without being obliged to give any reason. I understand that my data can be withdrawn up to the point of data analysis and that after this point it may not be possible.		
I hereby freely and fully consent to participate in the study which has been fully explained to me and for the information obtained to be used in relevant research publications.		

Participant's Name (BLOCK CAPITALS)

Participant's Signature

Investigator's Name (BLOCK CAPITALS)

Investigator's Signature

Date: